

Reciprocal Cooperative Learning in the Teaching of Reading Comprehension

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ABSTRACT

Reciprocal Cooperative Learning by Annemarie Palincsar and Anne Brown (1984) examine changes in student reading comprehension when reading and the changes in how the students used the predicting, questioning, and summarizing strategies. The techniques ask students to employ four strategies: predict what they will read, generate questions about what was read, clarify any ideas that were not understood in the reading, and summarize the main idea of the reading. The study was implemented in second grading period within the school year 2016-2017 in Jacinto P. Elpa National High School. This study made use the pretest-posttest quasi-experimental research design to determine the effectiveness of Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) as a reading comprehension approach. A pre-post test design without a control group, this requires collecting data on the study of participants' level of performance before the intervention took place (pre-), and to collect the same data after the intervention took place (post-). This study was used in tow sections which were both given the same treatment. The pre-test was given to both groups after which the intervencion was introduced to both groups, which was the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning. The Oral Reading Proficiency Test (ORPT) Result of the students from the previous school year was used as a secondary data to establish the real scenario of the reading profile of the students regarding Word Recognition and Comprehension. The data were processed employing the weighted mean and T-Test. By the findings, the following conclusions were derived: Students still needs to be exposed to reading materials and other avenues where English is the medium. Results showed that most of the students still belong to the Instructional level regarding Word Recognition. Regarding Comprehension, majority of the Grade 8 populace belongs to the Frustration Level.

It connotes that even at their level they still have not developed reading comprehension strategies to aid them in comprehending a text read. The scores of the students in the four strategies of the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning namely; Predicting, Clarifying, Questioning and Summarizing increased. Thus Reciprocal Cooperative Learning was effective in improving the students' Reading Comprehension Skills.

KEY WORDS: *Reciprocal Cooperative Learning, Teaching Strategy, Reading Comprehension, Predict, Clarify, Question, Summarize*

1. INTRODUCTION

Reading comprehension is an integral part of learning a second language. Although it can be said that it is possible to learn a language by listening and speaking, without reading comprehension, the language learner has limited hope of learning new vocabulary and stagnates with what oral productive knowledge he has obtained (Egilsdóttir, 2012). This study aims to make use of Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) as an alternative way to teach Reading Comprehension skills to the students.

Cooperative learning is an instructional method whereby students in small groups collaborate to maximize one another's learning and to achieve mutual goals. A recent shift has occurred toward English reading instruction that is more student-centered and communication-oriented (Pan & Wu, 2013). Language learning, specifically reading requires more cooperation and interaction. Cooperative learning is one of the most remarkable and fertile areas of theory, research, and practice in education. In the past three decades, collaborative learning has become a widely used instructional

procedure across different grade levels and subject areas according to Johnson (2000) and cited by Adams (2013).

Despite the several studies and researches made over the past years, it cannot be denied that the problem in reading comprehension still exists. As a matter of fact, in the School Year 2015-2016 the Oral Reading Proficiency Test Pre Test for the Grade 8 Students from Jacinto P. Elpa National High School was conducted. The result was a disappointment with 821 students tested for Comprehension only 153 students or 19% fall under the Independent Level, 175 students or 21% plunged into the Instructional Level and 493 students or 60% plummeted to the Frustration Level.

According to the National Reading Panel (2007) cited by Novotny (2011), three important elements are needed to promote comprehension. First, vocabulary development and vocabulary instruction; second, comprehension strategies to facilitate an active thoughtful process between the reading and the text, and third, development of teachers to learn and help students apply comprehension strategies. Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) advocates these three elements and thus prompted the researcher to conduct this study with the use of Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) with the aim to enhance the reading comprehension skills of the students.

Theoretical / Conceptual Framework

Education anchored with the Humanism theory (Petrovska, 2015) targets self-actualization and autonomy of those who learn, respect their interests and needs and encourages internal motivation. A humanistic approach encourages students to evaluate their learning and take control of it. Affective goals are valued in addition to cognitive ones; students are seen as capable people who should have the freedom to take the initiative and to develop learning objectives that they see as relevant to their needs and interests.

Reciprocal Cooperative Learning fits particularly well with this perspective, as it provides students an alternative to the teacher-fronted classroom. Inside the classroom and in the use of RCL, learning is self-actualized in a cooperative and supportive environment. Students act as the facilitators of their

learning together with their classmates, which meet the affective goals of learning.

Learners are diverse, and each one entails a particular intelligence. The theory of Multiple Intelligence implies that teachers must recognize and teach in a broader range of talents and skills that depend on a variety of intelligence. It is on this premise that the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) is used. Groups work with four (4) members with each one assigned a particular comprehension strategy. Students learn cooperatively with one another who has different multiple bits of intelligences

A variety of multiple intelligence activities highlights the students' Multiple Intelligence. Students learn to appreciate each other's gifts and skills while they see the diverse abilities and usefulness while they perform the structure of cooperative learning (Avila, 2016).

This study made use of a particular Cooperative Learning Strategy which is the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) it was developed based on Vygotsky's theory of the fundamental role of social interaction in the development of cognition. Developed by Brown and Palincsar in 1984, Reciprocal Cooperative Learning calls on students to become "the teacher" and work as a group to bring meaning to a text. Students engage in dialogue regarding parts of the text (Fales, 2011). It is a collaborative technique in which students; first make a prediction about the text through visual clues or base on the title of the text then, they will read a passage of text, paragraph by paragraph. After reading they will then pause for clarification which include; questions on word meaning, unclear phrases, and ambiguous sentences. Questions will be generated as to their understanding of the read text and the way they relate to the characters. The last part will be the Summary where important ideas are gathered and students may retell the story in their words.

Laguador (2014) emphasized that collaboration among the group members improves the skills of the students to communicate in social discussion and participate in the accomplishment of their common goal. Low-performing students may tend to give up on performing his activity alone but with the help of high performing students.

Figure1. Schematic Diagram of the Study

In this study the concepts are illustrated in the schematic diagram which is depicted in circles. The uppermost circle is manifested as the independent variable of the study which presents the Student's Reading Profile regarding their Word Recognition and Comprehension based on the Oral Reading Proficiency Test was the dependent variable of the study as represented in the diagram. It was used to identify the different reading proficiencies of the learners; frustration level, dependent level and independent level. It served as a secondary data for this study.

On the other hand the second circle represents the independent study or the process to be applied to the respondents, the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL).

The 3rd circle is the proposed training design for teachers based on the findings revealed in the investigation, after the research has come full circle the questions were answered and the objectives were attained. It is the output of the study.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to test the effectiveness of the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) as a Cooperative Learning approach in increasing the reading comprehension of the students.

It supports to answer the following specific questions:

1. What is the reading proficiency profile of the Grade VIII students in Jacinto P. Elpa National High School as to:
 - 1.1 Word Recognition; and
 - 1.2 Comprehension?

2. How effective is Reciprocal Cooperative Learning in enhancing the reading comprehension of JPENHS Grade 8 students as to:
 - 2.1 Predicting;
 - 2.2 Questioning;
 - 2.3 Clarifying; and
 - 2.4 Summarizing
3. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test when Reciprocal Cooperative Learning was used?
4. What is the proposed training design for teachers based on the findings of this study?

Hypothesis

Problems 1 and 2 are hypothesis free. Problem 3 is hypothesized as follows:

Ho 1: There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test when Reciprocal Cooperative Learning was used.

Significance of the Study

The entities listed below are believed to be the beneficiaries of this output:

The Administrators: The outcome of this research would provide innovative insights and valuable information and would provide a clear picture of the real scenario inside the classroom. Moreover, this study would introduce a cooperative approach that is both be beneficial to the students and teachers.

Subject Coordinators/Supervisors: This study would be an eye opener to the school which would enable them to plan out more inputs to ensure that cooperative learning strategy would attain its goals of quality education.

Teachers: As the forefront of education, this study would provide the teachers valuable insights and open their eyes to a different way of handling the class. The Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) would improve their way of teaching and provide a better avenue for developing the social and interpersonal skills of their students. The teachers would be able to benchmark in providing meaningful activities in the classroom.

Students: The students are the endpoint; they would embark on a new academic journey which would widen their horizon regarding cooperative learning. This study allows them to enhance their social and interpersonal skills while providing them activities

that would ensure a meaningful and lifelong learning. Students learn cooperatively with the give and take relationship cultivated by cooperative learning with the goal of enriching their Reading Comprehension skills.

Parents: As first teachers of the youth, they could help promote communication competence inside the home. The strong partnership forged by the school and the parents in the academic pursuit of their child is very vital. Without the continued support of the parents in the academic endeavors of their child, all efforts will go to waste.

Future Researchers: The findings of this study would be of great help to all individuals who would pursue their academic journeys. It will also aid them in gaining further research ideas, pertaining to the topic of this investigation.

Scope and Limitation

This study was limited to the cooperative learning strategy particularly the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) in Grade VIII students under the Special Science Curriculum. The study was implemented in the second grading period within the school year 2016-2017. It was conducted at Jacinto P. Elpa National High School, Tandag City, Surigao del Sur. Two sections under the Special Science Curriculum were utilized in the study. There were 30 students in each section, the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) will only be applied in the second grading of the school year. Only one teacher, the researcher, will handle both sections.

Definition of Terms

The following terms are operationally and conceptually defined to promote a better understanding of the study.

Clarifying: As a comprehension strategy in Reciprocal Cooperative Learning helps the students monitor their learning through clarifying difficult and unfamiliar words, unclear sentences and passages.

Cooperative Learning: It refers to students in small-group learning instructional strategy of working together on a shared task as simple as solving math problems together in multi-step, or developing a design of a new school. In this study, each member is accountable for the task and role assignments. Teacher Vision1 (2015)

Cooperative Learning Strategy: It refers to a pedagogical approach wherein students are gathered into small groups to accomplish a given task at hand.

Frustration Level: It is when the child clearly struggles to read. Errors are numerous. The child produces words without natural rhythm and in an unnatural voice.
(thudscave.com/~lamplighter/reading.htm)

Independent Level: It refers to a reader who reads with no more than one error in word recognition in each 100 words and has a comprehension score of at least 90 percent.
(thudscave.com/~lamplighter/reading.htm)

Instructional Level: It refers to a child who reads with no more than one word-recognition error in approximately 20 words. The comprehension score should be 75 percent or more.
(thudscave.com/~lamplighter/reading.htm)

Oral Reading Proficiency Test (ORPT): It refers to the secondary data used to determine the Students' Reading Proficiency Profile. It is an oral reading test conducted by the teacher during the start and end of the school year.

Predicting: As one of the four comprehension strategies in the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) this is defined as the foretelling of the future events based on the cover of the book, pictures in the text or title of the selection.

Questioning: In Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) is the act of employing questions to increase awareness of the important ideas in the text read.

Reading Comprehension: It is one of the pillars of the act of reading. When a person reads a text he engages in a complex array of cognitive processes. He is simultaneously using his awareness and understanding of phonemes (individual sound "pieces" in language), phonics (connection between letters and sounds and the relationship between sounds, letters and words) and ability to comprehend or construct meaning from the text.
(www.k12reader.com/what-is-reading-comprehension, 2016)

Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL): It is a process involving four distinct activities (questioning,

clarifying, summarizing and predicting) employed in a student-led, team approach to develop reading comprehension skills among primary students.

Summarizing: In Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) is one of the comprehension strategies that involves recalling and arranging essential parts of the text read.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter presents the reviewed literature and studies which are relevant to the present study.

Related Literature Foreign

An article published by Teacher Vision1 (2015) as cited by Avila (2016) Cooperative learning is an instructional strategy with a shared task by a group of students. Each member is accountable for any part of the shared task. It also discusses five primary elements of small-group learning such as a) Positive Interdependence; b) Face-to-face interaction; c) Individual and Group Accountability; d) Group Behaviors; e) Group Processing. If well implemented cooperative learning leads to achievement, active learning, student discussion, confidence, and motivation. The skills develop when collaborating with the group are different with the skills by working individually.

Cooperative Learning is particularly beneficial for any student learning a second language. Cooperative Learning activities promote peer interaction, which helps the development of language and the learning of concepts and content. It is important to assign English Language Learners to different teams so that they can benefit from English language role models. ELLs learn to express themselves with greater confidence when working in small groups. In addition to 'picking up' vocabulary, ELLs benefit from observing how their peers learn and solve problems (colorinColorado.org).

One way of promoting early development of reading comprehension and critical thinking skills is to teach primary students a metacognitive approach to reading. Metacognitive practices combine three components of reading knowledge: a general cognition of the reading process; awareness of personal strengths and weaknesses; and literacy of the purpose for which the reading is being undertaken. Metacognitive readers

are aware that: focused attention is required to comprehend text; attention wanes over time; attention is greater if the reading material is interesting; and comprehension enhanced if the material is familiar. Metacognitive readers are aware of their proclivities and maximize their strengths and minimize their weaknesses (Cooper & Greive, 2011; Krause, Bochner & Duchesne, 2003).

Metacognitive reading strategies can be taught at all levels and one way of mentoring young readers to be metacognitive is to employ the procedures of Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) (Cooper & Greive, 2011; Center, 2005; Laverpool, 2008). Moreover, in this approach reading is done with a purpose readers only pursue the information that is significant to this purpose. Information necessarily gained from this endeavor is then put on record by metacognitive readers. As a result, metacognitive readers plan for reading, monitor their process and then judge the results of reading.

The Reciprocal Teaching methodology has a robust evidence base, includes a cooperative learning style, metacognition is supported throughout, and progress is monitored in line with implementation science. Specifically, Reciprocal Teaching is an instructional approach and dialogue based framework based on the skills necessary for good comprehension. The approach is based on practitioner's explicitly teaching four key strategies and facilitating high-quality discussion (West Dunbartonshire Council, 2015).

Teacher Vision (2015) published an online article in which they wrote; when implemented well, cooperative learning encourages achievement, student discussion, active learning, student confidence, and motivation. The skills students develop while collaborating with others are different from the skills students develop while working independently. As more businesses organize employees into teams and task forces, the skills necessary to be a "team player" (e.g., verbalizing and justifying ideas, handling conflicts, collaborating, building consensus, and disagreeing politely) are becoming more valuable and useful. Using cooperative groups to accomplish academic tasks not only provides opportunities for students to develop interpersonal skills but also gives them authentic experiences that will help them be successful in their future careers.

Cooperative Learning does not only develop the reading comprehension skills of the students, but in their interaction with one another their fluency in the language also increases. One of the most salient features of cooperative learning is communication; cooperation within the group cannot exist without communication. According to several teaching theorists, enhancing speaking skill is through the communicative activities which comprise an information gap, a jigsaw puzzle, games, discussion, and Role-playing. Also, Hedge (2000) supports this idea that the activities that can assist better speaking skills are free brainstorming and role-playing. Harmer, (2001) states that the language activities are important factors in teaching language for communication. The activities should create interaction and discussion space among the students in the classroom and also with the teacher. Additionally, Oradee (2012) adds that "communicative activities can stimulate the students and establish positive relationships between the teacher and the students; as well as among the students thus, encouraging a supportive environment for language learning.

Local

DepEd Order 31. S. 2012 identified cooperative learning strategy integrated to be integrated into the different learning areas as stipulated in Enclosure No. 1 to attain the DepEd's vision and mission. The K to 12 Basic Education Program discussed the Junior High School in the article of PCDSPO/DEPED/GOV.P (2013) with its implementation for the students to undergo immersion with earn-while-you-learn opportunities in their chosen track for experience and relevant exposure.

Villanueva and Almario (2010) Effective instructional approaches in dual language instruction primarily draw from teaching models employed in second language learning. To those involved in second language learning, curricular themes arising in dual language instruction will sound familiar, and these are namely balanced literacy, cooperative pedagogy, student-centered learning, thematic units, content-based instruction, and integration.

According to Siddiqui (2003) mentioned by Oradee (2012), the available research on second language attainment expose that to develop and learn a language, learners must interact in the language. Increasing the occurrence and diversity of the verbal

association in which learners participate is a vital purpose of any coaching based on the principles of second language attainment. The teacher-fronted approach often ends up avoid students from having real interactions with the teacher and fellow students because the teacher starts and controls the reciprocal action. Collaborative learning promotes reciprocated interaction and by increasing the number of chances available for verbal expression, offer opportunities for a vast variety of communicative functions than those found in teacher-fronted classrooms.

Related Studies

Foreign

Reciprocal Cooperative Learning, has been used widely abroad; it has been to be an effective cooperative learning strategy across multiple disciplines and subject areas such as Math, Science and Social Sciences. Studies were made across the globe; United States of America, United Kingdom, Taiwan and Hong Kong to name a few and the results were astounding.

Pan and Wu (2013) conducted an experimental study on Taiwanese English for Foreign Language Freshmen students regarding the use of Cooperative Learning in Reading Comprehension and Learning Motivation. It was found out that students receiving RCL instruction performed significantly better on English reading comprehension examinations than students who were taught using traditional lecture instruction. For different proficiency levels of groups, the medium- and low-proficiency groups benefited more in English reading comprehension from cooperative learning instruction than from traditional lecture instruction. Cooperative learning instruction also created a significantly positive effect on student motivation toward learning English reading.

In a study conducted by Cooper & Greive (2011), a pre-service teacher found out that the students of the experimental group, which was exposed to the reciprocal cooperative learning benefited from the use of the strategies in ways other than knowledge of the content of the readings. They gave evidence of finding the process interesting and were enthusiastic about their involvement. The process provoked curiosity and caused them to engage with the ideas within the readings. They also gave evidence of internalizing the strategies of questioning and clarifying. Finally, students' involvement with the reciprocal cooperative learning strategies changed the

way they viewed the reading process. They appeared to implicitly see the process of reading as more than the decoding of text; it had become a way of deciphering the meaning implied by the readings. As such, it was recommended that the reciprocal cooperative learning could be extended to all other subject areas that include subject-specific text, such as Science, History and others.

Reciprocal Cooperative Learning also proves to be an effective learning strategy not just in a regular classroom setting but also when used for students with learning disabilities as such reciprocal cooperative learning address this problem by helping students internalize concepts first learned through social interactions. Palincsar and Brown's reciprocal cooperative learning model consisting of the four strategies of prediction, summarization, question generation, and clarification was used by Klingner and Vaughn in a study to teach reading comprehension to English Language Learners with Learning Disabilities. Using this approach, the teacher first models the use of these comprehension strategies through think-aloud while reading the text. The teacher then leads students in a text-related discussion, guides them in practicing strategy use, and provides corrective feedback. When students become proficient at using these strategies, they take turns leading their peers in discussions about texts.

In connection to that, Klingner and Vaughn found that reciprocal cooperative learning improved reading comprehension for both groups of English Language Learners with Learning Disabilities. The students who profited the most from the reciprocal strategies had a higher initial reading ability (decoding at grade 4 and above) and oral language proficiency. They also suggested that a range of students can benefit from this strategy (i.e., students who have problematic decoding skills, students who have low comprehension skills, students still gaining proficiency in English, etc.) and that the benefits to students continued even outside of the limits of this study. One of the reasons that reciprocal strategies work is the high level of student engagement, as it is the students who are "teaching" each other when discussing text passages on their own. Once this is achieved, the teacher does not need to remain with one group to ensure progress – he or she can circulate and monitor all groups as needed.

Adams' (2013) study of the cooperative learning strategies attempt to raise students' achievement, and student literacy is increased as well which has been positively connected to student performance. Teachers face different options to choose a cooperative learning strategy. Characteristics of cooperative learning strategies are individual accountability, social skills, positive interdependence, face-to-face interaction and group processing. Cooperative learning techniques increase student retention and motivation of learning lessons which can have a positive impact in the classroom. Cooperative learning is learning situation where education occurs while two or more students work together for a shared task to be completed. It is different from a teacher-centered approach where the teacher implements learning strategies of cooperative learning techniques.

In the years 2014-2015 the West Dunbartonshire Council conducted a Hub Project entitled "Reciprocal Teaching: Raising Attainment through the Development of Higher Order Thinking Skills," with approximately 900 the study made several findings. The lower achieving group scored 30% or less on the pre-test assessment of which there were 447 pupils, and the higher achieving group scored 70% or more on the pre-test assessment of which there were 370 learners. There were increases in the Comprehension assessment of the lower achieving group of up to 23% in every chapter of the lessons conducted. The higher achieving group also demonstrated improved comprehension scores. The scope for change in the higher achieving group is much less compared to the low achieving group. At the follow-up assessment, some children in the high achieving group scored the maximum at each stage. Therefore, there is a ceiling effect. Nevertheless, the mean difference at the baseline assessment between the low and high achieving groups was 57.5% and this reduced to 30.8% at follow-up.

Moreover, from the same study in the aspect of Higher Order Skills, the lower achieving group demonstrated increases in the skills with the greatest difference in pupil ability to analyze and evaluate text indicating that Reciprocal Cooperative Learning is linked to the improvement of higher order skills. The higher achieving group shows no change in the mean score for understanding, however, the score remains above 85%. The greatest changes for the achieving group follows a similar pattern to the lower achieving

group with noticeable development in the skills of analysis and evaluation.

In an English Class in China, a study was conducted by Wang (2012) employing cooperative learning and the traditional method of teaching. Cooperative learning proved to be effective. Each group member is responsible not only for his learning but also for helping group members. Thus, every member can have a sense of achievement. The students found it easier and enthralling to talk with the partners in English because the group activities involved the students' interest and their favorite topic. They said that they were always eager to share the information with their members.

A study from the University of Illinois in 2010 on the use of RCL among Science students proved to be a success. Students used their knowledge to make a reasonable prediction about what they thought they would be reading and learning. Even though the students' predictions were not always correct, the comprehension strategy of predicting engaged them in thinking about what they were reading. It led to valuable classroom discussions. Good readers continually ask themselves questions throughout the reading process, but formulating questions can be a challenging and complex task. Through reciprocal teaching, the students learned to generate questions about the text's main idea and important details, improving their reading comprehension skills. The students were reluctant at first to share words or ideas that they had trouble understanding. However, when asked to identify a word or idea that a classmate might have trouble decoding or understanding, they were able to find and share much more. Problem-solving became more explicit through the process of clarifying unknown words that the students came across while reading. Clarifying helped the students to monitor their comprehension while they were reading, and allowed them to identify problems that they encountered while reading portions of text or difficult words. When the students were able to recognize and clarify difficult words or confusing parts of text while they were reading, they became more strategic readers. The students looked for clues to help them connect their understanding, instead of reading on and not comprehending what they were reading.

Furthermore, in the same study, it was found out that summarizing was the hardest reciprocal teaching strategy that the students encountered. Summarizing required the students to recall and arrange in order

only the important events in a text. Summarizing improved the students' reading comprehension and allowed them to construct an overall understanding of the text. Many of the students needed modeling and more scaffolding to help them with this strategy.

Local

A study conducted by Cabansag (2013) at Isabela State University on Attitudinal Propensity of students toward strategies in English Language Learning cited Cooperative Learning as one of the factors affecting language learning along with age, prior knowledge, attitude, motivation, aptitude, amount of exposure. Anxiety in second language learning have been shown to be strongly related to the choice of language learning strategies.

However, Altamira (2013) pointed out that some students experience undesirable memories. One or two does the work while others just sit down and relax but having the same grades altogether. Other dominant students because of their intense desire for a good grade stifle the contribution of their team mates' efforts. Still others divided the work for which other teammates know nothing about the other parts of the assigned task. Other students avoid some projects altogether. To avoid these unpleasant occurrences and situations, it should maximize the learning satisfaction that is a result of a high-performance team. Kagan Cooperative Learning Program defines cooperative learning through basic principles such as simultaneous interaction; individual accountability, equal participation; and positive interdependence.

In addition to the prior studies cited is an experimental study in a geometry class by Manlunas (2012) conducted to sophomore students at UP High School in Cebu. Two sections were utilized both were ICT integrated and only one was employed with cooperative learning as a pedagogical approach. Findings have shown that the combination of ICT and cooperative learning proved to be more successful regarding student achievement. Students who work in small groups on geometry problems using geometry software showed improvement on higher-level problem solving and applying mathematics applications and received significantly higher scores on standardized final exams.

Furthermore, Brain-based and second language acquisition research has shown that the old school method—assign a chapter, take a test, and discuss the

test—will not result in quality and depth of thought. Language teachers who want to update, refresh, and rejuvenate their teaching should apply mind/brain learning principles, as described by Caine and Caine (1994) cited by Fontanillas (2013). Language teaching can be stimulating to the learners if it involves hands-on activities that will cater to individual and the group's different learning styles.

Fontillas (2013) further expounded that a teacher may use some examples of music and film lessons like peer teaching and group projects particularly those that promote group construction of knowledge. It will allow a student to observe other students' models of successful learning, and encourage him or her to emulate them. It depicts social constructivism, self-efficacy, learning styles; varying instructional models that deviate from the lecture format, such as visual presentations, site visits, and use of the Internet. It enhances multiple intelligences, learning styles, self-efficacy. It also results to varying expectations for students' performance, from individual written formats to group work that includes writing and presentation, interpretation of theatrical, dance, musical, or artistic work, and performance of actual tasks at a performance site attribution theory, conscientization, multiple intelligences, learning styles. It affords choices that allow students to capitalize on personal strengths and interests self-efficacy, bits of intelligence, learning styles. The overt use of socio-cultural situations and methods that provide authentic contexts and enculturation into an academic disciplinary community social constructivism and conscientization is also manifested. The course material that demonstrates valuing of diverse cultures, ethnic groups, classes, and genders conscientization, learning styles are also considered

Lucena and San Jose (2013) concluded in their study that learning environment in the 21st century must be ones in which students should be actively engaged in learning activities and with each other. Students nowadays should be well-rounded to increase their competitiveness. Cooperative learning offers a proven and practical means of creating exciting social and engaging classroom environment to help students to master traditional skills and knowledge as well as develop the creative and interactive skills in today's society.

Laguador (2014) study on Cooperative Learning Approach in an Outcome-Based Environment discussed teaching and learning which is a student-centered approach recommended at this point especially in the outcome-based education where the facilitator of learning activities are the teachers rather than using the method of a traditional lecture. This research discusses the option of cooperative learning approach to encourage active participation of the learners. The output of the teaching-learning process is the academic performance which is an important measure in the learning experiences of the students. The active participation of the students is required in the classroom while encouraging strengthening affective and cognitive ability and psychomotor domains. An important aspect of success is the Outcomes-based education to which the learning outcomes gained from the cooperative learning is an essential effort on quality education for the future leaders of the world.

Synthesis

The literature and studies reviewed herein have bearings on the present study being conducted. Cooperative learning has long been proven as an effective strategy in increasing learners' achievement; in Math, Science, Social Studies and particularly is language learning, specifically in reading comprehension. Reciprocal Cooperative Learning as a pedagogical approach has long been proven effective. In an attempt to raise the reading comprehension level of the students it is deemed by the researcher to try out this strategy as it was effective based on some studies conducted here and abroad. Cooperative learning principles take advantage of heterogeneity in classes by encouraging learners to learn from one another and more and less knowledgeable peers. Communication and interpersonal skills are developed, reading comprehension and fluency are improved and lasting relationships and bonds made. Bonds thus develop among learners who can lead to increased understanding and acceptance of all members of society, a benefit of cooperative learning that expand beyond the walls of the school itself.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter describes the methods of research used with a brief description of the research design, research instrument, data gathering procedure, statistical treatment and the selection of the respondents of this study.

Research Design

This study made use of the pretest-posttest quasi experimental research design to determine the effectiveness of Reciprocal Cooperative Learning (RCL) as a reading comprehension approach. A pre-post test design without a control group, this requires collecting data on the study of participants' level of performance before the intervention took place (pre-), and to collect the same data after the intervention took place (post-). This study was used in two sections which were both given the same treatment.

The Pre-test was given to both groups after which the intervention X was introduced to both groups, it was the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning. In the study of both groups, the pre-test O_1 assessed the reading comprehension of the students. The posttest O_2 of each group was then compared.

Experimental Group	O_1	Time	O_2
		X	
Experimental Group	O_1	X	O_2

Research Subjects

The respondents of this study were the Grade VIII students enrolled at Jacinto P. Elpa National High School for the school year 2016-2017. Three Grade VIII English class was assigned to the researcher, but only two sections were utilized for this study. Grade 8 sections Schwann and Schleiden are the subjects of this study. Each class was composed of 30 students per section. Both sections were the experimental group, thus undergoing treatment. Students are sectioned homogeneously based on their previous general average, as such it ensured that two sections were comparable.

Sampling Procedure

To determine which section will not participate with the intervention method the researcher used the "purposive sampling", this was done due to the homogeneous grouping of the students based on their academic performance. All three sections handled by the researcher were comparable based on their academic performance but only 2 were chosen to participate.

Research Setting

The study was conducted at Jacinto P. Elpa National High School, located at Capitol Hills, Telaje, Tandag City. It is the leader school of all the Secondary Schools in the Division of Tandag City.

JPENHS holds the majority of the population in all the secondary schools in Tandag City Divison. It has a total population of 3,384 students, 105 mentors, ten non-teaching staff, 6 Head Teachers and one school Principal IV. Specifically, the setting of this study was the Grade 8 English classes handled by the researcher.

Research Instrument

The research instrument used for this study is a Standardized Reading Comprehension Test from Florida Comprehensive Assessment Test. It is a 50-item test with reading passages together with comprehension questions. Since the research instrument to be used is a standardized test there is no need for validation. This particular text was selected because the literary, biographical, and informative texts are similar to the reading material the students encountered in the classroom. The theme or topics used in the selections are also widely used or is generic. The data collected with this instrument was analyzed to uncover changes in the students' reading comprehension before they had been taught reading strategies then after they had learned and practiced using the techniques.

The secondary data used for this study is the result of the Oral Reading Proficiency Test (ORPT) from S.Y. 2015-2016. The text and questions used were from the CARAGA Regional Office of the Department of Education. The selection for the test is "The Black Widow" which has 252 words. After orally reading the text the students was asked five comprehension questions which they answered orally as well. At the start of the school year all grade levels are instructed to conduct the ORPT to assess the students' reading profile regarding word recognition and comprehension.

Data Gathering Procedure

The study was conducted for two grading periods. In the first grading period, no treatment was introduced. On the start of the second grading, the pre-test was conducted, answers were checked and tallied afterwards. This grading was also utilized as the period for the treatment which is the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning. The students were oriented and they were responsive on all activities that transpired inside the classroom. Lesson plans for the second grading can be found in the Appendix of this study. It utilizes the 4A's format; Activity, Analysis, Abstraction and Application. Literary texts used in the Lesson Plans are of Afro-Asian origin as mandated by

the Curriculum Guide provided by the Department of Education.

In the experimental class, the students was be grouped by 4, each one of them has a distinct task to be carried out in the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning according to Cooper & Greive (2011);

Predicting: At critical points in the reading of the text students are to pause to draw and test.

Clarifying: While the text is being read; students are to critically evaluate the meaning of unfamiliar words and phrases and to draw upon the collective knowledge of the team members. Also, they are to seek the essence of ideas, focal ideas and themes contained in the text.

Questioning: The text is read, and questions are posed about the content. When evaluating the text, students are to concentrate on the main ideas and check their level of understanding.

Summarizing: When summarizing, students are to re-state the main ideas and themes in their own words to ensure that they have fully understood them.

By the end for the grading period the same questionnaire was conducted as the post-test.

Initially, teachers closely monitor the implementation of the four strategies, stepping in to correct and scaffold student-efforts. Over time, the student-run teams are to take increasing responsibility for the process, permitting the teacher to progressively remove him- or herself from team mechanics and to concentrate on facilitating and managing the process (Cooper & Greive, 2011; Brown, 1986; Palincsar & Brown, 1986).

After the period of treatment, the students were then given the questionnaire. The result of the post-test was be recorded and compared with the result of the pre-test to see if there was an increase in the scores of the students which in effect determine their reading comprehension skills.

Statistical Treatment of Data

For the analysis and interpretation of the data, the following statistical tools were used:

Problem 1, as stated in Chapter 1 of this study was described using weighted mean. To determine the proficiency level of the students this scaling was used:

	Word Comprehension (Average errors committed)	Comprehension (No. of correct answers)
Independent Level	96-100	5
Instructional Level	91-95	4
Frustration Level	89-90	3-1

Problem 2, as stated in Chapter 1 made use of Mean and Percentage to determine if the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning was effective on increasing the reading comprehension level of the students. To determine whether it was effective or not a Pre-Post Variance was set. It was done because a standard interval could not be set because the number of items per strategy was different.

Problem 3, to test the significant difference between the pre-test and post-test was treated using the t-test.

4. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter includes the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered. The sequence of the discussion of all the problems is based on how the problems are set in Chapter One.

Reading proficiency profile of the Grade VIII students in Jacinto P. Elpa National High School in terms or Word Recognition and Comprehension.

Figures 2 and 3 shows the secondary data used for this study which is the result of the Oral Reading Proficiency Test during the School Year 2015-2016. The presented table deals with the students reading proficiency profile regarding word recognition and comprehension.

Figure2. Level of Proficiency of Students in Word Recognition for S.Y. 2015-2016

It can be gleaned from the Figure 2 that most of the Grade 7 students which are now in Grade 8 and the subject of this study in terms of word recognition fall under the Independent Level with 327 students of the entire populace. The 304 students are under the Instructional Level and 282 students or 31 percent on the Frustration Level respectively.

Similarly, Oradee (2012) mentioned that in second language attainment, learners must interact in the language. Increasing the occurrence and diversity of the verbal contact in which students participate is an important purpose of any coaching based on the principles of second language attainment.

Figure3. Level of Proficiency of Students in Comprehension for S.Y. 2015-2016

The secondary data used a pre-existing data. It was done as it was deemed by the researcher significant to be able to establish the scenario of the reading profile of the students.

On the other hand, their Comprehension Level provides a different scenario. Only 12 percent is in the Independent Level while 36 percent is on the Instructional Level and a majority of the students with 53 percent falls under the Frustration Level. It goes to show that the problem in reading comprehension is still existent. Students may be able to decode words but comprehending it as a whole is still a challenge for them.

As stressed by Cooper and Grieve (2011), metacognitive practices combine three components of reading knowledge: a general insight of the reading process; awareness of personal strengths and weaknesses; and the idea of the purpose for which the reading is being undertaken. Metacognitive readers are aware that: focused attention is required to comprehend text; attention wanes over time; attention is greater if the reading material is interesting and comprehension is greater if the material is familiar. Metacognitive readers are aware of their proclivities and maximize their strengths and minimize their weaknesses.

Figure4. Level of Proficiency of Respondents in Word Recognition and Comprehension

To establish the reading proficiency of the students now, it was deemed necessary by the researcher to provide this data which presents the data based on the Oral Reading Proficiency Test (ORPT) conducted at the start of the school year. The data presented only contains the reading profile of the students who were subjected to the intervention; Sections Schwann and Schleiden.

For Word Recognition majority of the students from both section fall under the Independent Level which is also the same with Comprehension. On the other hand, although the students belong under a specialized curriculum there are still students that fall under the Frustration Level for Word Comprehension. It implies that even at their level the students still lack the necessary reading comprehension skills needed to understand a text read fully.

Moreover, as Faldo (2010) cited the findings of Villamin (2003) stated that the eight factors that influence the acquisition of reading ability are motivation, home background, the attitude of/toward parents, siblings, teachers, and peers, motor ocular coordination, auditory discrimination, language facility and interest and intelligence. Furthermore, the learners lack some of these, their reading performance becomes less from the standard.

Furthermore, in a study conducted by Diep (2010), the gender and monthly income of parents are related to the reading comprehension of the students. Likewise, based on all available research conducted in the last 24 years on factors affecting reading comprehension, the following conclusions were derived: research on vocabulary as a factor affecting reading comprehension was found to be limited. It was found out that intelligence, vocabulary, and reading ability were significantly related. Research on sentence structure as a factor affecting reading comprehension revealed that reading comprehension was a function of the similarity of the oral patterns of language structure used in reading materials. Research on the rate of reading as a factor affecting reading comprehension revealed that the ability to retain verbal information was a function of intellectual ability. Questioning and purpose setting as factors influencing reading comprehension manifested that questions at the end of the passage enhance the retention of the prose material.

The Effectiveness of Reciprocal Cooperative Learning in enhancing the reading comprehension of Grade 8 students in the four comprehension strategies

Figure on this presents the Pre-Test and Post-Test Average scores of the respondent who were subjected to the intervention and the summary of its result.

Figure5. Computed Pre-Test and Post-Test Average on the Four Comprehension Strategies of Section Schwann

During the Pre-test the strategy with the highest average is Clarify with 7.07 while the lowest is Question with 5.83. Post-Test result shows that Clarify had the highest average with 9.27 while at 7.73 Summarize had the lowest average among the four comprehension strategies. Considering the table all score for the four comprehension strategies increased from the pre-test to the post-test; Predict at 2.7, Clarify at 2.2, Question at 2.73 and Summarize at

1.9. The variance is set as an indicator for the mid-score in the comprehension strategies. If the post-test score overlaps the variance, it can, therefore, be concluded that the particular strategy is “Very Effective” if not then it is “Effective.” As can be gleaned from the Figure 5 no comprehension strategy overlapped the variance, so all strategies were effective.

Figure6. Computed Pre-Test and Post-Test Average on the Four Comprehension Strategies of Section Schleiden

The average of the Pre-Test and Post-Test scores of section Schleiden are the Table 5. In the Pre-test, the strategy with the highest average is Clarify with 7.07 while the lowest is Summarize with 5.23. The Post-Test result shows that Clarify had the highest average with 9.37 while at 8.1 Question had the lowest average among the four comprehension strategies. Considering the table all score for the four comprehension strategies increased from the pre-test to the post-test; Predict at 2, Clarify at 2.3, Question at 2.27 and Summarize at 2.97. The variance is set as an indicator for the mid-score in the comprehension strategies. If the post-test score overlaps the variance, it can, therefore, be concluded that the particular strategy is “Very Effective” if not then it is “Effective.”

Reading Proficiency Test. Students like the Clarifying part of the RCL because it introduces them to unfamiliar words and they enjoy using the dictionary in finding out the meaning of the unfamiliar words. Fontanillas (2013) stressed that language teaching could be stimulating to the learners if it involves hands-on activities that cater to individual and the group’s different styles.

On the other hand, scores for Question and Summarize fall behind the other two comprehension strategies. In the Pre-Test and Post-Test of both sections Question and Summarize would always have the lowest average scores. It can be noted that most of these students belong under Independent Level for Word Recognition while a majority also belongs to the Frustration Level for Comprehension. While students know the words but they fall short in answering comprehension questions and summarizing the main idea of the text.

It can be noted that in both section Clarify had the highest average scores for both the Pre-Test and Post-Test which we can correlate with a huge population of students under the Independent Level for the Oral

Figure7. Percentage of Scores of Correct Responses in Pre-Test and Post-Test in Section Schwann

Figure 7 shows the Percentage of scores in the correct responses of the students from their Pre-Test to their Post-Test. Pre-Test results show Clarify as the highest with 54.36% and Predict being the lowest at 47.14%. As observed from the graph Clarify had the highest Average score at 71.28% from the post-test while Predict was the lowest at 64.52%. It can be concluded that from this section Clarify was the most developed reading comprehension skill while Predict was the least developed.

Similarly, in a study from the University of Illinois in 2010, it was stressed that problem solving became more explicit through the process of clarifying unknown words that the students came across while reading. Clarifying helped the students to monitor their comprehension while they were reading, and allowed them to recognize problems that they encountered while reading portions of text or difficult words. When the students were able to identify and clarify difficult words or confusing parts of text while they were reading, they became more strategic readers.

Figure8. Percentage of Scores of Correct Responses in Pre-Test and Post-Test in Section Schleiden

On the other hand, Figure 8 shows the Percentage of scores in the correct responses of the students of Section Schleiden from their Pre-Test to their Post-Test. Pre-Test results show Clarify as the highest with 54.36% and Summarize being the lowest at 47.58%. As what we can see from the graph Summarize had the highest Average score at 74.55% from the post-test while Predict was the lowest at 48.1%. It can be concluded that from this section Summarize was the

most developed reading comprehension skill while Predict was the least developed.

However in a similar study conducted at the University of Illinois in 2010 it was concluded that summarizing was the hardest reciprocal teaching strategy that the students encountered. Summarizing required the students to recall and arrange in order only the important events in a text.

Table1. Summary of Results on the effectiveness of the RCL in two sections

	Pre-Test Average	Post-Test Average	Variance	Adjectival Rating
SCHWANN				
Predict	6.60	9.03	10.30	Effective
Clarify	7.07	9.27	10.03	Effective
Question	5.77	8.50	8.88	Effective
Summarize	5.83	7.73	8.41	Effective
Over-All	25.27	34.53	37.68	Effective
SCHLEIDEN				
Predict	6.73	8.73	10.36	Effective
Clarify	7.07	9.37	10.03	Effective
Question	5.83	8.10	8.91	Effective
Summarize	5.23	8.20	8.11	Very Effective
Over-All	24.87	34.40	37.43	Effective

Table 1 would answer Problem number 3. It shows how effective the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning is in two sections. To test if it was effective, Average scores from the Pre-Test and Post-Test were computed. After doing so the mid number was then calculated through adding the pre-test average and the number of items. It was done per strategy because not all strategies have the same number of items. The test whether such strategy was effective was done through

determining if the post-test average is equal to the mid-number then it is “effective” but if the post-test average is greater than the mid-number then it is “very effective”. After doing so, it was found out that all comprehension strategies were effective except summarizing which is found “very effective”. Overall Reciprocal Cooperative Learning increased the Reading Comprehension Skills of the students.

Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test with the RCL

To answer Problem No. 3 the following table will present the data gathered and the statistical tool used to treat it.

Table2. Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test with RCL

SECTION	DF	Computer P Value	Decision	Conclusion
Schwann	49	5.94	Reject Ho	Significant
Schleiden	49	1.59	Reject Ho	Significant

As gleaned from Table 6 both sections have a *df* of 49 and *t* computed value for section Schwann is 5.94 while section Schleiden is at 1.59 which rejects the hypothesis of having no significant difference. Hence, their difference from the pre and post-test is significant. On the same ground, the study of Laguador (2014) on Cooperative Learning Approach in an Outcome-Based Environment discussed teaching and learning which is a student-centered approach recommended at this point especially in the outcome-based education where the facilitator of learning activities are the teachers rather than using the conventional method. This research discusses the option of cooperative learning approach to encourage active participation of the learners. Hence, students learn more when they are in control of their learning.

Reciprocal teaching has been proven to be a technique requires that not only students know how to

comprehend, but calls for teachers to learn how to teach important comprehension strategies so that students understand why they are using them and can successfully use them without teacher prompting. Reciprocal teaching requires students to become self-regulated learners who have the knowledge to choose from several strategies to accomplish a reading goal. Through reciprocal teaching, students are taught how to use and coordinate multiple strategies while they are reading, which aid in their understanding and comprehension.

THREE DAY SEMINAR-WORKSHOP ON LEARNING STYLES, MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES AND RECIPROCAL COOPERATIVE LEARNING

Introduction

Reading comprehension is still one of the problems a language teacher encounters in his/her career. A

student may be well-oriented with words used in a text but probing questions would show poor comprehension of the text read. Reciprocal Cooperative Learning as found out by this study increased the reading comprehension of the students. The strategy asks students to employ four strategies: predict what they will read, generate questions about what was read, clarify any ideas that were not understood in the reading, and summarize the main idea of the reading.

This Seminar – Workshop Matrix aims to reorient the teachers on the use of Cooperative Learning as a Learning Strategy. Cooperative Learning as a pedagogical approach is anchored to the students' varied learning styles and multiple intelligences.

With an emphasis on Reciprocal Cooperative Learning, this Seminar-Workshop will retool teachers with an appropriate reading comprehension strategy

that aims to increase the reading comprehension levels of the learners.

Objectives

1. To provide a comprehensive understanding of Reciprocal Cooperative Learning as a Cooperative Learning strategy that aids the reading comprehension skills of the students.
2. To encourage the use of Multiple Intelligences and Learning Styles in cooperative learning groupings.
3. To equip language teachers with necessary cooperative learning strategies to cater 21st century learners.

Participants

The participants of this Seminar-Workshop are the English Teachers of Jacinto P. Elpa National High School. On the other hand, the resource speakers will be the Master Teachers of the said school and the Division Education Program Supervisors.

Table3. Training Design for RCL

RECIPROCAL COOPERATIVE LEARNING TRAINING MATRIX		
TOPIC	OBJECTIVES	PERSONS INVOLVED
Learning Styles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognize the diversity of learning styles • Create learning environments that are conducive to optimal learning experience. • Demonstrate sensitivity to individual learning needs and the learning environment and • Show flexibility and spontaneity in meeting the needs of diverse learning styles 	Mrs. Tessie F. Anino
Multiple Intelligences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reorient Howard Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences; • compare the theory of multiple intelligences with traditional theories of intelligence; and • explore the implications of the theory of multiple intelligences for schools and society 	Dr. Jeanette R. Isidro
The Teaching of Reading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • develop reading strategies : experience reading in a shared context • read and respond : To develop response to texts (narrative, fiction, non-fiction) • Utilize existent reading strategies that will help students comprehend the text read 	Mrs. Ma. Isabel Loayon
Cooperative Learning Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retool teachers with Cooperative Learning Strategies applicable to language learning • Guide teachers in the use of cooperative learning to promote student achievement 	Dr. Ponciano G. Alngog
Reciprocal Cooperative Learning: An Overview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduce Reciprocal Cooperative Learning as a Reading Comprehension Strategy • Assist teachers scaffold student learning by modelling, guiding and applying the strategies while reading. 	Zyx Raxie R. Cuartero

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present studies relative to the conduct of RCL in a language classroom 	
Predicting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers will be able to help students: • Generates logical predictions • Provides evidence to support predictions • Identify clues to help make predictions 	Dr. Evelyn C. Coro
Clarifying	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers will be able to help students: • Identify ideas for clarification • Uses strategies to clarify words and ideas • Define words based on context clues 	Mrs. Fe E. Lagumbay
Questioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers will be able to help students: • Make simple recall questions • Generate main idea questions • Formulate Inferential questions 	Mr. Antonio M. Tinunga
Summarizing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers will be able to help students: • Make concise summary • Use thinking maps, mind maps, graphic organizers, etc. to plan their summary. 	Mrs. Edna H. La Torre

5. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents a summary of the study including the findings, the conclusions drawn from the findings and the researcher's recommendations.

Summary of Findings

The results revealed that in terms of word recognition, most of the students fall under the instruction level. For comprehension most of the students are on the frustration level. Reciprocal Cooperative Learning was effective in aiding the reading comprehension skills of the students in all comprehension strategies namely: Predicting, Clarifying, Questioning, and Summarizing. Moreover, it was found out to be Very Effective in terms of improving the students' Summarizing skills. Among the four comprehension skills, Clarifying and Summarizing were the ones that were most developed; while, Predicting was the least one. There was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the students using RCL.

Furthermore, it was a surprise to have the component of Summarize as the most developed together with Clarify while Predict was the least developed among the four comprehension strategies. At the beginning, when asked about their summaries, specified that it was hard for them to choose details in the passage was the most important.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it can be inferred that students still needs to be exposed to more reading materials and other avenues where English is the medium. The result showed that most of the students still belong to the Instructional level in terms of Word Recognition. Exposure to reading materials could help them become Independent Learners. The value of reading can be developed if materials are provided and the habit of reading is not only encouraged at school but also at home.

In terms of Comprehension, majority of the Grade 8 populace belongs to the Frustration Level. It implies that even at their level, they still have not developed reading comprehension strategies to aid them in comprehending a text read. Although students can decode the words and pronounce it, correctly but understanding how it is used contextually still needs to be developed. The problem with Reading Comprehension is still existent and it needs to be addressed as soon as possible.

Cooperative Learning is a great avenue for students to take control of their own learning and create first-hand experiences that could make their learning more meaningful.

It can be implied that students enjoy strategies that are interactive and hands-on. Interactive strategy like

Summarizing requires students to listen to prior exchanges of ideas and make a summary after such. Students listen attentively to the summaries made as it will enable them to answer comprehension questions afterwards. Some learners may have felt more comfortable seeking clarification of confusing vocabulary with the use of the dictionary and concepts within the small group setting. Learners appeared to enjoy the dialogue as they interacted with each other and the text. When students talk and interact among their group members, they are more likely to voice out their opinions or ideas and this encourages them to explore the text in a more intensive way. Predicting being the least developed among the four comprehension skills, implies that students give less importance to this skill as predictions are mere observations like the title of the book and its cover would oftentimes be incorrect. Thus, they hesitate to give in-depth predictions of the fear of being wrong.

Recommendations

Armed with the empirical data, the researcher would like to make the recommendations that the school could allocate more funds in improving the library facilities in order to attract the frequent visit of the students. Deepening the value of reading for the students would enhance their word recognition and comprehension. In the classroom, teachers are encouraged to use the Reciprocal Cooperative Learning in teaching Reading Comprehension as it was found out to be effective in increasing their reading comprehension skills. For learners to have a meaningful learning experience, the use of strategies that centers on the learners on-hand experience where they will be able to work together and collaborate is also encouraged. Future researchers are fortified to have another experimental study on Predicting as a Reading Comprehension Skill in RCL as to why this skill came out least developed and how to fully develop it. School administrators are encouraged to implement the training design derived from this study as it was supported by the findings of this study.

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